

THE ROLE OF STRATEGY IN THE ORGANIZATION OF MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES

Izzatullayeva Madinabonu Yolkin girl

Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics 70411201-2nd-Level Master's
Student, Majoring in Management (by Industries and Sectors), Uzbekistan

Abstract: The article highlights that production ravines in industrial enterprises and their management are an extremely complex system, but that managing them with strategy gives great opportunities. Alternatively, as a management backbone, there are ways to choose an alternative strategy for the development of industrial enterprises, as well as an in-depth study of the strategy for achieving the goal.

Key words: Enterprise Management Process, strategic plan, Strategic Management, competitiveness, innovative potential, nostrategic management, symbiosis, consumer demand, planning.

In the process of enterprise management, it is necessary to carry out activities such as directing the organization towards the goal, implementing strategic plans and tasks of managers, bringing the chosen strategy to life. Strategic management is a management plan aimed at strengthening the position of the enterprise, meeting the needs of customers and achieving certain results. The establishment of a management system at enterprises arises from the creation of management that is fully consistent with the organization of production and its type, and the need for the fulfillment of all functions in the management of production technical, economic social and financial activities of each branch of Management in a market economy. The solution to these problems is management reform effective distribution of management functions by conducting a series of activities to clearly define the management goal. But in the current market conditions, many enterprises and organizations, in particular project organizations, still have excessive links in the management structure, which, as we said above, negatively affect the decrease in labor productivity in strategic management and, ultimately, the final activity of the enterprise. Therefore, in the context of liberalization of the market economy, it is important to adapt the strategic management system at enterprises to market requirements. The strategy consists of an event-a set of measures that management uses to ensure the success of the enterprise. Management creates a strategy to know how to manage an enterprise business, as well as to correctly choose one of the alternative directions in a multi-factor

environment. The strategy that the management decides to use indicates that one of the available business areas and a specific way of doing business has been chosen. The enterprise should separately set financial and strategic goals. The unavailability of financial goals causes financial resources to be spent at high risk. As a result, the growth and competitiveness of the enterprise decreases.

The strategic goals of the enterprise are therefore important that they strengthen the competitive position of the enterprise and indicate the direction of business development. A strategy is the creation of a unique and convenient position, which implies a certain set of types of activities. The content of taking a strategic position consists in creating a bunch of types of activities that outperform competitors. The creation of a strategy raises the problem of basic management-that is, it shows how the desired results can be achieved, taking into account the current and future capabilities of the enterprise. The term "strategic management" was introduced into circulation in the 60s and 70s to reflect the difference between high-level management and current management at the level of production. As the main idea reflecting the essence of the transition from operational management to strategic management, the high priority became the idea of the need to shift the focus to the external environment in accordance with changes in the environment in a manner and in a timely manner. Consider a number of definitions proposed by influential manufacturers of strategic management theory. In the case of Strategic Management, the organization is concerned with the change in the environment and the conditions of the life of the organization, in order to achieve the goals of foresight in the future, at each present moment it is precisely what is in strategic management from the future to the present. The actions of the organization in the present period, which ensure a certain future to the organization, are determined and carried out. It is also characteristic of strategic management that not only the foreseeable state of the enterprise will be noted in the future, but this is also considered one of the most important tasks of Strategic Management, the ability to exert a counter-influence on the surrounding changes, which gives the opportunity to achieve the intended goals. Secondly, the development of a resource program in nostrategic management begins with an analysis of the internal capabilities and resources of the organization. In such an approach, the organization can only determine what amount of product to produce and how much to act on it. The volume of production and the amount of costs created by the firm cannot respond, the market determines in what quantity and price the product will be purchased. Strategic management is more a certain philosophy or ideology of business and management. By each manager, it is understood and

implemented in a certain sense differently. Of course, there are a number of recommendations, rules and logical drawings for the analysis of problems and the choice of strategy, as well as the implementation of strategic planning and the practical realization of the strategy. But in general, strategic management is a symbiosis of high leadership intuition and art in communicating an organization to strategic goals, high qualifications and creativity of servants and, finally, the active introduction of all employees to the implementation of organizational tasks, the search for the best ways to achieve their goals.

The strategy is considered a management plan aimed at strengthening the position of the firm in a general way, meeting the demands of consumers and achieving the goals set. Choosing a clear strategy means choosing the most optimal one from within the various possible ways and methods of development. The firm management plan includes the following main functions and divisions: supply, production, finance, marketing, personnel, scientific research and development. Choosing a strategy means dividing business solutions and competitiveness efforts into a single system. Strategy development is one of the main functions of managers. Some managers develop a strong strategy, but cannot bring it to life. Other managers also develop an average strategy and skillfully implement it. The better thought out and skillfully implemented the strategy, the stronger the position of the company. Well-established companies in management also face unexpected unpleasant situations. Ultimately, a good strategy will set the stage for a successful performance, despite strong position in the market, unforeseen circumstances, strong competition and internal problems. Strategic planning is a management process that focuses on developing company development goals and ways to achieve them. Strategic planning provides the basis for enterprise management, unites the entire company and covers all its levels. Strategic planning is not just the task of the management, it should be involved in IT employees of all levels of the company. The main concepts of strategic planning include the mission of the company (the definition of the company's task), values, basic competencies (what the company does better), the vision of the future (the future image of the company for a year or two), strategic problems (systemic problems that prevent the achievement of goals), tasks aimed at overcoming strategic problems and According to experts in the field of management, the entire planning and management system should be directed to the interest of employees in improving the quality and efficiency of work, which is an important condition for the development of the firm. However, it does not come as little as other successful ones. This requires skillful organization, scientifically based planning and

management, in addition to resource bases. Especially important is the material interest of people in the labor of production, which today is called the quality of Labor life. The strategy allowed to form a common idea for the future. And the planning process itself, and the direct strategic plan, is a gift of clarity, individuality to the enterprise, which allows it to attract certain types of employees and not attract other types of employees. This plan will open up prospects for the enterprise and attract new employees, in addition to producing products, it will help to sell it.

List of literature used:

1. A.Rakhimov, M.Ravshanova and M.Aliyeva. Econometric analysis of increasing efficiency of industrial enterprises. E3S Web of Conferences 458.
2. R.M.Makhmanazarovna, The importance of a synergy approach to teaching an economics in the direction of the economy. International conference on multidisciplinary research and innovative technologies, 5-7 (2001).
3. A. N.Rakhimov, J.S. Eshankulov, The mechanism of increasing the economic power of production in industrial enterprises. Economy and education. No 6 of 2022.